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Role of Indigenous Magars in Promotion of Green Economy

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Abstract

The term 'Sustainable Development' is a worldwide popular buzzword and extremely desired and digested agenda of development. Environment is considered as the foremost aspect in the development interventions. The concept of sustainable development goals was emerged and aligned with people, planet and prosperity. In recent years, the concept regarding sustainable development has been changed. Now, the concept of Green, Resilient and Inclusive Development (GRID) is emphasized as sustainable development. In the context of Nepal, the GRID concept is being internalized. While considering the federalism as one of the best governance systems, it has envisioned the equitable, inclusive, prosperous Nepal and the Nepalese society. GRID prevails and promotes the green economy, where indigenous peoples live their dignified life by enjoying individual and communal rights and promoting their culture, identity, and economic prosperity. There is high potentiality of promoting green economy and achieving the GRID-goals if meaningful participation and role of the indigenous communities are promoted. This article discusses the concept of green economy and its promotion through accelerating roles of Magar indigenous community.

Key Words: *Magar(s), Indigenous people, GRID, Green economy, development.*

Introduction

Concept of Green Economy

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) defines a “green economy” as one that results in improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities (UNEP, 2011, p.1). A green economy

can be thought of as one which is low carbon, resource efficient and socially inclusive. In a green economy, economic growth and employment should be driven by public and private investments that reduce carbon emissions and pollution, enhance energy and resource efficiency, and prevent the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services (Al-Taai, 2021). It is emphasized that the investments in the economy should be corresponded, considered and address the environmental issues so the sustainable development is achieved. These investments need to be catalyzed and supported by targeted public expenditure, policy reforms and regulation changes. The development path should maintain, enhance and, where necessary, rebuild natural capital as a critical economic asset and as a source of public benefits, especially for poor people whose livelihoods and security depend on nature (UNEP, 2011, p. 2).

The concept of a “green economy” is not the replacement of the concept of “sustainable development” but also more focus and a growing recognition of the environmental issues that directly contributes to achieve the sustainability rests almost entirely on getting the economy right. This concept has been welcome a new engine of economic growth. As considered, it builds on an innovative system of economic activities that enhance social well-being, nurture flourishing natural environments and yield competitive yet responsible business growth. Stimulating transformation, the green economy encourages and facilitates progress towards the three pillars of sustainable development - people, planet and profit (EMG Worldwide, 2016). It can be concluded that this concept is related to reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcity in a way that results the increased wellbeing and social equity.

Moreover the concept of green economy in equally combined with environmental, economic and social aspects of the society, nations and the world as a whole. Towards a Green Economy, focuses on 10 key economic sectors because we see these sectors as driving the defining trends of the transition to a green economy, including increasing human well-being and social equity, and reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities (UNEP, 2011, p. 5).

More than 60 countries around the world have started the journey towards the green economy, with many seeking to achieve their ambitions within a few decades (EMG Worldwide, 2016). The governments pioneering this transition are doing away with the

traditional line of thought that there is an inevitable trade-off between economic progress and environmental sustainability, instead showing significant opportunity for investment, growth and security.

History of Green Economy

Industrial revolution and mounting modern development interventions gradually created pressure over environment. In the name of advancement and focus on fast-paced development, development activities started to damage the environment and its degrading trend is still continue. To address this environmental issues, the affected nations started to raise this issue and held the top level dialogue. Consequently, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) was established after the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm in June 1972 and aimed to coordinate the responses to environmental issues within the United Nations system – in world. Then environmental issues became a mainstreamed agenda in the United Nations and started to focus to address the issues in the initiation of the United Nations through its UN agencies led by UNEP. The concept of green economy emerged in against the global trend of circular economy. Circular economy focuses on resources cycling and recycling for sustainability and relating to the people and the economy (Hope, 2022),

The term ‘green economy’ was first coined by a group of leading environmental economists of the United Kingdom (UK) in a report entitled “Blueprint for a Green Economy” prepared for and submitted to the UK government in 1989. This report was prepared by the David Willian Pearce, Anil Markandya, Edward Barbier on behalf of London Environmental Economics Center (LEEC). It is also popularly known as the Pearce Report, which was prepared for the Department of Environment of UK government. This report presented, first time, the practical policy measures for ‘greening’ modern economies and putting them on a path to sustainable development (Pearce, Markandya and Barbier, 1989 as cited in Pearce, Markandya and Barbier, 2013). Among these authors, Barbier and Markandya published “A New Blue Print for a Green Economy” with highlights on the achievements in the past 20 years and focusing on what more needs to be done to generate a truly ‘green economy’

in the 21st century (Barbier and Markandya, 2013). Then, the concept of green economy became popularized and started to synchronize it in the economic as well as developmental aspects in the developed countries.

It seems that the goals of a green economy are broader, comprehensive and ambitious, but they are not new – it has been conceptualized dates back to Agenda 21, a ‘blueprint for sustainable development’, adopted during the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio, however, despite progress made, greater efforts are needed (UNCTAD, 2011). In this context, the “Rio+20 Conference, 2012” also focused on promoting the green economy as a catalyst to accelerate progress on sustainable development in the globe. The Rio+20 conference aimed and drew attention of the world to build support for a green economy that yields win-win outcomes for the environment and economy, and for developing and developed countries.

The UNCTAD as an intergovernmental organization within the United Nations, promotes the interest of the developing countries in development and trade. So, not only the UNCTAD but also all UN agencies, international organizations are seriously raising the issues of environment with specific focus on reducing the risks and promoting sustainability. Dozens of international conferences like Conference of the Parties to the UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD COP), the UNCCD is one of the three Rio Conventions – along with the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED, or Earth Summit) etc. are some of the globally renown initiatives. Besides, sustainable development goals (SDGs) targeting to achieve by 2030 is also primarily focus on environment (planet) along with people and prosperity. In other word, environment is considered as a core element and focus in the SDGs.

SDG-13 (Climate Action) aims to take action to combat climate change and its impacts. There are five targets under this goal, they are (1) Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries, (2) Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning, (3) Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning, (4) Implement the commitment

undertaken by developed-country parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change to a goal of mobilizing jointly \$100 billion annually by 2020 from all sources to address the needs of developing countries in the context of meaningful mitigation actions and transparency on implementation and fully operationalize the Green Climate Fund through its capitalization as soon as possible, and (5) Promote mechanisms for raising capacity for effective climate change-related planning and management in least developed countries and small island developing States, including focusing on women, youth and local and marginalized communities (UNDESA-SD, 2024). This mandate has created pressure to all nations and the government. Nepal has been implementing the SDG localization guidelines.

Research Methodology

This article has been prepared based on the findings of a qualitative research – mainly focused on analytical research design. This research was focus on policy analysis and review and analysis of issue related literature. Mainly, national and international conventions, reports, laws and articles available in internet access were consulted, reviews and analyzed for this research. Due to the nature of the research, field based survey was not carried out so the primary data and quantitative data are not presented in this article. Findings and analysis are presented as narrative form.

Key Findings And Analysis

The major findings and analysis of the study are presented in this section- as follows:

Nepal's Policies and Practices supporting to Green Economy

The Constitution of Nepal has guaranteed a "Clean Environment" as a fundamental right [Article 30]. It indicates that environment issue has become the individual's fundamental rights' issue and it should be conserved. The environment conservation and working in this sector is concurrent rights of federation, province and local levels of Nepal. So they deserve power, authority and duties on this sector. Federation holds the key and leading role for this sector especially national policy making, localizing internal conventions

and fulfilment of commitments, and guiding to province and local levels with financial support. Province and local level also can formulate the necessary policies and laws in the territories aligning with international and national policy, frameworks and guidelines. Indeed, local communities and the local levels are directly related and more affected if any environmental hazards occur.

The government of Nepal has endorsed National Climate Change Policy, 2076 (2019) envisioning to greenary environment and the sustainable development. This policy has set a goal to contribute to socio-economic prosperity of the nation by building a climate resilient society. Besides There are 7 objectives – such as enhacnging climate change adoption capacity, building resilience of ecosystem, promotion of green economy, mobilizing national and intenation financing, mainstreaming and integration of climate change issure related policies, conducting research & effective technologies development, mainstreaming gender equality and social inclusion (OPMCM, 2024). The government of Nepal has committed to Nationally Determined Commitment (NDC) to reach at least 20 percent of the annual budget by 2026. However, presently budget allocation to the environment sector if less than 5 percent of the annual budget of the government of Nepal.

Prior to this policy there were also climate change related policy and plan like ‘The Climate Change Policy, 2011’, and strategies and programs, ‘National Adoption Plan’ (NAP) framed under this policy. This initiative was focused on environmental conservation and reducing risks and increasing community resilience capacity. Climate change issues are considered and introduced in the periodic development plans of all three tiers of governments of Nepal and also in other relevant plans and programs. Environmental assessment has become the mandatory provision for medium and large scale projects, and before planning for excavating and selling of river related resources. All federal units – federal, provincial and local levels should work seriously in the environment sector. So that all these constitutional, legal and policy provisions ensures the state’s responsibility and accountability towards conservation of the environment – more specifically promotes the green economy and climate change adaptation initiatives.

On behalf of the Government of Nepal (GoN), National Planning Commission (NPC) submitted a ‘Nepal Status Paper: United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development 2012 (Rio+20)’ in November 2011. Such report focused on review of policies, progress and institutional frameworks by covering three pillars namely ‘Economic pillar’, ‘Social pillar’, and ‘Environmental pillar’ (NPC, 2011, p.1). The green economy has been considered as an instrument for sustainable development, poverty reduction and inclusive and equitable economic growth. Economic growth must be sustainable, supported by well-functioning markets and preferential access for green products at price that reflect the scarcity value of natural resources (ibid, p.3)

Magars and Environment-Sensitive Livelihood Patern

In term of population size, Magar indigenous community (people) is the third largest among all caste and ethnic communities of Nepal. But, they are in the first position among the 60 ethnic communities who are legally recognized by the government (NFDIN, 2002). Magar community is one of the eldest indigenous ethnic communities in Nepal and its origin is considered to the western regions – presently Gandaki, Lumbini and Karnali provinces (Baral Magar, 2066 BS). Typical culture, own mother tongue, indigenous knowledge, skills, technologies, customary laws and system, traditional institutions, traditional belief and practices are their tangible and non-tangible heritages and properties. They reside all over the country – Nepal – all 77 districts, and in more than 80 countries outside of Nepal. Collectiveness or unity among diversity in culture, mother tongue, history and historical background, social and cultural practices (Magar, 2079 BS). It is special and unique identity of Magars that is rarely found even in other indigenous communities in Nepal.

Since Magars are living all over the country and mainly in the rural area, they are still dependent on local natural resources, and to some extent, to the date, they have access to resources. Besides, they have had own indigenous knowledge, skills, technologies, customary laws and traditional practices for managing resources (Baral Magar, 2066 BS, Thapamagar, 2008). That used to significantly contribute for sustainable use and management of the natural resources, and

ultimately the conservation of the environment. An impact study carried out in predominantly agricultural and heavily forested landscapes within Pakistan's Hindu Kush Himalayan (HKH) region shows that functional community-based organizations (CBOs) for developing farming communities at the village level is positively correlated with a farmer household's decision to adopt agroforestry (Ullah, Mishra and Bavorova, 2023, P. 957).

A study also seems that, as a livelihood practices, there is several synergistic relations with household welfare, indigenous knowledge and socio-ecological systems in rural areas of Nepal (Bharadwaj, Pullar, Seng To and Leary, 2021). Like other indigenous people, Magar community are primarily dependent on agriculture since their long history of civilization. Their traditional way of livelihood was associated with natural resources, for instance, agriculture, livestock farming, cottage and micro enterprises, mining and so on (Magar, 2071 BS; Magar 2077 BS). Sustainable way of utilization and management of locally available natural resources has been practicing by the indigenous peoples since their existence and livelihood was primarily dependent on them.

Role of Magars for Green Economy

Indigenous custom and traditions are also related to their indigenous livelihood, occupation, labour and employment (Yatru, 2020, p. 107). In case of Magars, they have own indigenous custom, tradition, occupation, livelihood strategies and practices based on their indigenous knowledge system, skills, technologies, belief and customary laws (Magar, 2075 BS and Thapamagar, 2008). Large number of population, scattered in all over the country and sustaining their livelihood especially based on agriculture and/or informal sector and remittance senders from foreign employment are directly contributing to the national economy – that may or may not be formally accounted and recoded. On the other hand, Magars were also involved in mine excavation in rural areas especially in Magar territory like Gandaki, Lumbini province (Shrees-Magar, 2066 BS). They were popularly known as Gurkhas in the world in general and in UK, Hongkong, Singapore, India in particular as an Army.

Magars livelihood is not only related to local natural resources and their indigenous ways but also adoptive, environment-sensitive, risk-free and sustainable. In other word, their livelihood strategies

and practices are traditionally environment friendly, supportive to the green economy and GRID model. However, it is not advance or high-technology adoptive. Their practices are appropriate technology friendly and based on sustainable approach. Agriculture, agro-forestry, forestry, river-resource, indigenous knowledge, skills and technology based occupation and livelihood activities are their own. All these are not only associated with their subsistence level of livelihood but also a compartment of multiple aspects of their life as well as the economy as a whole. For example, natural resources like water, forest, land, wind all are necessary and associated with their social activities, social functions, cultural activities – which ever connected in their live from womb to tomb.

Magars have their indigenous knowledge and skills, and customary practices of managing and utilizing the natural resources (Thapamagar, 2008). Their livelihood mainly depends on traditional agriculture including agro-forestry and livestock. Their way of working for agriculture is more labor-intensive and based on their customary practices and system like Arim-parim (Baral Magar, 2068 BS). Magars are not only using the natural resources but also protecting more sustainable ways due to the importance (compulsory required) for their culture, social functions and so on. Their belief system and practices also contributing to protecting the natural resources, flora and fauna species, and the ecosystem in the nature. It is broadly covering all kind of ecosystem – environmental, social and economic. Hence, their involvement and role is very crucial for both local level and national level economy of Nepal, and more specifically to promote the green economy.

In this way, Magar community is considered as one of the key contributors for promoting green economy and it is in the newly emerged concept of indigenomics (indigenous economics) (Hilton, 2023). Even in (for) the modern or advance economy, their culture, eco-friendly livelihood and economic activities, tangible and non-tangible socio-cultural heritages can also be the highly potential ingredients for tourism sectors. Cultural tourism, eco-tourism, agro-tourism, sports tourism, nature-health tourism and other types of tourism can be flourished and developed as a key sector of the modern economy. That will immensely contribute in other sectors of the economy. Thus, Magar community can play significant role not only to promote the green economy but also to develop and scale up the whole economy of Nepal. Although it needs to be started from

earns more foreign currencies, gradually declines the trend of youth migration for foreign employment and shortage of human resources in the country. Economy potentiality (from local to national) will be flourished and youths migrated to the abroad can return back or/and whose who stay there permanently can be involved in the business and trade of products that produced in the Magar communities.

In initial phase, there would be need of investment (financial support and policy support) from the government side but later Magar communities can generate necessary capital themselves and heavily contribute in generating tax and non-tax revenue to the government. On the other hand, government's huge investment for environment sector – especially for climate change adaptation, disaster preparedness and response, will not be necessary due to the results of this kind of initiatives. And, then government can invest such budget in other sectors. Some major development infrastructure like road-transport, electricity, ICT etc. are necessary. The foremost precondition is the government's policy (that might be began from local levels/governments) and creating best-fit environment. At least local levels of the Magar territories should join-hand with Magar community and start to adopt this indigenomics development model.

Opportunity of IT and Digital Economy for Magars

There is still high potentiality of agriculture, cottage, micro and small industries, herbal, agroforest, culture and other local resource related business and enterprises if indigenous knowledge, skills and technologies of the Magar community can be utilized, revitalized and promoted (Magar, 2071 BS). There should be generate the innovative ideas so that advanced but appropriative technologies (like information and communication technologies) should be used. But there should not be compromised the culture, identity and other indigeneity related threats. Capitalism, globalization and ICT have creating both positive and negative effects, and much more are negative to the indigenous peoples.

With emerging concept of green economy and GRID model, all that can be used for expected impacts (benefits) if they are used an means (not the end) by aligning and addressing the issues concerning to the indigenous peoples. For example ICT should be used for right

to information and ensuring public (social as well) accountability, and promoting their business, expanding markets and linking with wider networks. And, that networks should not be limited only at local level; it should be expanded to the international level or globally (Magar, 2079 BS). Obviously, there might be several challenges and unexpected threats can rise but it should be assessed, identified the mitigation measures and adopted the appropriate policies and strategies effectively.

Magars have reached in over eighty countries in the world due to diverse purposes – many of them are for foreign employment. That is, to some extent, is a great opportunity to get exposure of outer world and getting back the better ideas, knowledge, skills, enhancing knowledge, earning money and financial resources, and utilize these for their own development. However, it is not being so as expected. The results are opposite and condition of the indigenous people – especially of Magars is very degrading. To some extent, Magars have started to jump in the modern economic activities like business, trade, entrepreneurship, and for that digital economy is creating vibrant environment of numerous opportunities. Number of Magars involve in the modern economic sectors is increasing and ICT, globalization and all most of capitals (human, social, physical etc.) play supportive role in their area significantly (Magar, 2075 BS and Magar, 2079 BS).

ICT and entering into the platform or system of the digital economy, there is also high potentiality not only for subsistent livelihood but also economic uplifting and getting prosperity in the Magar community. In conclusion, the global and national environment is being favorable and supportive if Magars are ready to revive their indigenous knowledge, skills, technologies, customary practices and culture concerning to the natural resources ultimately the environment.

Nepal government has endorsed the Digital Nepal Framework, 2019 for transforming the economy through application of ICT – with ambitious vision and approach. This framework covers the eight sectors – digital foundation, agriculture, health, education, energy, tourism, finance and urban infrastructure, and NRs 22 billion was announced for 80 initiatives (MOCIT, 2019). In this road map, federal

governments and local levels/governments are aggressively adopting digital governance, and connecting to the different sectors of the economy (MOCIT, 2079 BS).

Climate Change Adaptation as a Global to Local Agenda

In socio-ecological systems, social practices shape ecology and vice versa (Bharadwaj, Pullar, Seng To and Leary, 2021). The international initiative to address the climate change issue was started in 90s. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) was an international climate treaty finalized at the Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992 and came into force in March 1994. The convention has a key objective to curb and stabilize greenhouse-causing emissions in the atmosphere. It was a key first step in addressing global climate change. UNFCCC committee's meeting – popularly known as Conference of the Parties (COP) is held every year. COP28 [the United Nations Climate Change Conference] was recently held in Dubai, United Arab Emirates (UAE) from 30 November to 12 December 2023 in a global collaboration between countries (the parties) and various non-governmental actors with focus on assessing progress towards the goals of the Paris Agreement (<https://unfccc.int>). Climate disaster “loss and damage fund” was approved in this conference – that was already tabled at COP27 in Egypt last year (ibid). This fund is meant to support vulnerable communities and developing nations which are struggling to cope with the impact of climate disasters such as the destruction of crops caused by floods.

The UN conventions and other international conventions and initiatives are unconditionally emphasizing the conservation of the environment, and in promotion of green economy and GRID model globally. Nepal has already become a state-party so it should be responsible too. Nepal has expressed commitment in the international platform for ‘Nationally Determined Commitment’ (NDCs) – first in 2016 and second in 2020. On one hand it has created a moral pressure to Nepal for allocating annual budget for environment sector as well as taking appropriate initiatives (from policy to program).

On behalf of the Government of Nepal (GoN), National Planning Commission (NPC) submitted a ‘Nepal Status Paper: United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development 2012 (Rio+20)’ in November 2011. On the green-economy-theme, Nepal

shared the voice of developing countries that it should offer new trade opportunities to all countries, not become a pretext for “green protectionism” and raised the issue that high priority on sustainable transfer of new appropriate technologies to Least Developed Countries (LDCs) with strong institutional support, primarily contributing to a “just transition” and productivity enhancement that require for leading Nepal towards a low carbon but high and equitable economic growth path (NPC, 2011, p.2).

Nepal committed to the SDGs early on, and this commitment has been reaffirmed in key policy documents, such as the current 15th Plan and its 25-Year Long-Term Vision 2100 BS that internalizes the Goals (NPC, 2019). Nepal has prepared the SDG Status and Roadmap to localize the SDG indicators with baselines and targets for 2030. SDGs codes are assigned for all national development programs through the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework. Other key documents are a SDGs Needs Assessment, a Costing and Financing Strategy, and additional SDGs Localization Guidelines.

Nepal has conducted a Development Finance Assessment (DFA) to provide an overview of development finance flows and institutions and policies that can align finance with national development priorities (United Nations Nepal). Goal 13 is “Climate Action”- which is directly related to the climate change adaptation and climate change risk reduction measures – from national level policy making to building resilient community. Climate change action related initiatives have been reflected in the policy, periodic development plan and programs of all level’s governments. For that National Planning Commission (NPC) and Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration (MOFAGA) are playing leading role to roll out the SDG related and other national policies at provincial and local level by introducing their plan and programs. All these shows that climate change adaptation agenda has been assimilated from national to local levels in the current federal context of Nepal.

Magar Indigenomics for Green Economy

The concept of “Indigenomics” is a newly emerged concept however it is the far-former the modern economics. The term “Indigenomics” is a combined of “indigenous” and “economics”. The concept of indigenomics was coined by Carol Anne Hilton. She defines the term indigenomics a new yet ancient Indigenous

framework for building economies. It is considered as a new model of development that advances Indigenous self-determination, collective well-being, and reconciliation to the economic risks and opportunities that are arising from the global low-carbon transition (Hilton, 2023).

This concept advocates for issues of indigenous peoples in the perspective economics aspects by considering their rights, interest, culture, identity considering. Indigenous climate justice, sovereignty, self-determination, and risk management, and explore traditional Indigenous knowledge and data systems and the importance of elevating the role and voice of Indigenous stewardship in a climate action response.

Indigenomics, as a new word and concept, serves to call into visibility the relevance of an Indigenous worldview in today's modern economy (Hilton, 2021). It is the conscious claim to, and the creation of, space for the advancement of today's emerging Indigenous economy. For indigenous peoples, it is essentially a statement of claim their space in modern existence and modern economy. It is a call-out or invitation into an Indigenous worldview that seeks to put it into the center the concepts and experience of "development" and "progress" (ibid).

Indigenomics is considered as an about increasing the role and visibility of indigenous peoples in the economy. It is considered that this concept honors the powerful thinking of indigenous wisdom of local economy, relationships, and human values. So that this concept is necessary to advocate in the context of Nepal since about 40 percent of Nepal's total population is of indigenous peoples, required a new strategic way to revive the shrinking Nepalese economy and successful implementation of the federalism.

This concept emphasizes on increasing the role and visibility of Indigenous peoples in the new economy and understanding indigenous perspective. So that it needs to promote the meaningful participation and role of the Magars explicitly in the economy. It can positively impacted to the green economy as well as directly contribute in the GRID model of development. Likewise, indigenous knowledge skills, technologies and customary practice based occupations, livelihood and natural management systems will be revived and be accelerated.

On one hand it contributes to the modern economy (whatever as it is) in the strategic way of GRID model as well as promotion of the green economy which is very essential to the date. On the other hand,

if in case time passes, Nepal will lose the great opportunity to gain, and loss the capacity to restore the environment and unable to cope of devastating situation in the future. Furthermore, for Magar indigenous peoples, the concept of indigenomics directly contributes to their cultural values and practices, indigenous business development, local natural resource management, community empowerment and appropriate policy advocacy for their economic prosperity with explicit contribution to the green economy.

Discussion

Now, the global economy is facing a ‘triple crunch’. It is a combination of a credit-fuelled financial crisis, accelerating climate change and soaring energy prices underpinned by an encroaching peak in oil production. These three overlapping events threaten to develop into a perfect storm, the like of which has not been seen since the Great Depression. To help prevent this from happening we are proposing a Green New Deal.

The green economy is considered a vivid and ideal model of sustainable development, especially economic development, which affects all aspects of human life. It is worth noting that the role of sustainable development can only be activated by implementing the green economy program and providing a healthy environment. As for the concept of sustainable development, it is the exploitation of material and human energies, support and employment in an optimal manner, and work to develop them and increase their effectiveness in a way that guarantees the rights of everyone in the present and future, and includes people and natural resources, and affirms that the human being invested natural resources perfectly without depletion and leaves to future generations their right, and ensures the just distribution for the wealth (Al-Taai, 2021).

A study shows that several households and community-level factors influence smallholders’ timely adoption of agroforestry (Ullah, Mishra and Bavorova, 2023, P. 957). Magar peoples had their own indigenous knowledge, skills and technologies not only for sustaining their livelihood but also managing the locally available natural resources. For instance, they had/have agricultural lands on riversides and primarily adopted agroforestry to protect their crops from devastating effects of winds and floods. Nowadays,

agroforestry has been adopting as one of the sustainable ways of income diversification strategies for community peoples. In this way, agroforestry can be one of the better ways to Magars for uplifting their economic condition, protecting and promoting their indigenous knowledge, skills, technologies and customary practices, conservation of environment, and ultimately contributing in promotion of the green economy. This is a highly potential area in the context of Nepal.

Greening the economy can generate consistent and positive outcomes for increased wealth, growth in economic output, decent employment, and reduced poverty (Adhikari, 2012). Important policy decisions are needed to avert the likely costs of climate change and prevent the erosion of hard-won poverty reduction gains. Climate change is also likely to exacerbate the existing challenges to sustaining growth and poverty reduction, especially in the developing and least-developed countries of the region (ADB, 2011).

Conclusion

Application of green economy policy, GRID model and indigenomics model of development would be the sustainable solutions of climate change related issues and problems. As one of the largest population and scattered countrywide, Magar indigenous community can be a leading target group – initiator as well as beneficiary of these model. Deserving their indigenous knowledge, skills, technologies and customary laws and practices, can be revived, reused and promoted for improving their economic condition as well as contributing to promote indigenomics concept ultimately for implementing the GRID model and promoting green economy in Nepal. It would be effective and relevant to grasp the opportunity of presence of Magars in larger population and the countrywide. However, it would be better to start from Magar territories, where Magars' livelihoods are still depended and associated with local natural resources, and these resource management and mobilization practices are also interlinked with their culture, traditions, customs, and belief. These are great opportunities for both Magar community as well as the government – local, provincial and federal government in the current federal context. For this the federal government should play vital role by developing appropriate policy and creating favorable environment. At the meantime, Magar community (their associations)

should start initiatives from conceptualization phase and collaborating with local levels (governments) of the Magar territories. It could be win-win-win situation for Magars, local levels and the entire nation.

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